

**THE ANALYSIS OF THE LITERARY TEXT INCLUDES THE
PRINCIPLES THAT GUIDE IT AND EXPLAINS ITS MEANING**

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Annotation: The status of the text as a unit of speech above other units began to be scientifically recognized in the middle of the twentieth century. Today, text linguistics is a part of the civilization of scientific thought. Linguistics of text analysis can cover areas specific to the anthropocentric system. Therefore, the linguistics of literary texts has a great influence on the study of any language. The article discusses the urgency of this issue. The analysis of the literary text includes the principles that guide it and explains its meaning.

Keywords: text, literary text, linguistic unity, linguistic analysis, position, competence, text perception, text comprehension, interpretation.

Аннотация: Статус текста как единицы речи над другими единицами стал научно признаваться в середине XX века. Сегодня лингвистика текста является частью цивилизации научной мысли. Лингвистика анализа текста может охватывать области, характерные для антропоцентрической системы. Поэтому лингвистика художественных текстов оказывает большое влияние на изучение любого языка. В статье рассматривается актуальность данного вопроса. Анализ художественного текста включает в себя принципы, которыми он руководствуется и объясняет его смысл.

Ключевые слова: текст, художественный текст, языковое единство, лингвистический анализ, позиция, компетенция, восприятие текста, понимание текста, интерпретация.

Annotatsiya. Matnning nutq birligi sifatida boshqa birliklardan ustunligi XX asr o`rtalarida ilmiy jihatdan e`tirof etila boshlandi. Hozirgi kunda matn tilshunosligi fanning eng muhim sohalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Lingvistik matn tahlili antropotsentrik tizimga xos bo`lgan barcha sohalarni qamrab olishi mumkin, shuning uchun har qanday tilni o`rganishda badiiy matn lingvistikasi katta ta`sir ko`rsatadi. Maqolada ushbu muammoning dolzarbligi ko`rsatilgan, shuningdek, badiiy matnni tahlil qilish tamoyillari ochib berilgan.

Kalit so`zlar: matn, badiiy matn, til birligi, lingvistik tahlil, tamoyillar, kompetentsiya, matnni idrok etish, matnni tushunish, izohlash.

The search for text analysis, including the study of literary texts, gained new momentum, and the directions of text research began to be internalized. Text linguistics is the study of psycholinguistics, cognitive linguistics, gender

linguistics, ethnolinguistics, functional grammar, and cognitive linguistics, etc. supplemented with comprehensive research. New trends in the development of modern linguistic scientific thinking - expansionism (the emergence of new "dual" sciences through the intersection of several sciences) and anthropocentrism (aimed at comprehensive recognition of the "person in the language"), functionalism (aimed at studying the use of language, the meaning of use) and became the object of exploratory research.

A text is a place where all levels of language - from sound to sentence - function. However, the text should not be considered as a service environment, context only for other language units. It is also not just a concept related to one area of linguistics, such as syntax, but it is a complex unit of speech that can be recognized through comprehensive and in-depth, complex analysis. In this regard, the method of text analysis has become more complicated as "the highest and most multifaceted dynamic unit of speech, interconnected in terms of information, structure, and communication."

In the second half of the twentieth century, works on text theory began to appear. I.R. Galperin considered the text as an object of linguistic research. T.M. Nikolaeva showed two directions, formed by the peculiarities of text linguistics:

- 1) the direction that represents and analyzes the correctness of the text structure, and thus the correctness of communication;
- 2) to reveal the deep semantic aspects of a particular text.

That is, the necessary tools and principles for text analysis are provided. T.M. According to Dridze, "text is a unit of communication, the structure of meaningful information for communication and a defined method of organizing meaning, the implementation of reasoned and purposeful intelligent and thoughtful actions of the person, the desire to exchange material and practical interaction with other people and the analysis of linguistic and semiotic products".

I.R. Galperin himself said that the main character of the text is complete and has a title. However, some texts (lyrics, media text) may not have a title. Defines the text, expressing the views and opinions of foreign scholars on linguistic tools. I.R. Galperin considers: "A text is a purposeful and pragmatic device, combining different types of lexical, grammatical, logical, stylistic connections, with a literary connection to the document and a corresponding theme, with a complete idea, a speech". We learned from this definition that there is a parameter called speech, that is, it includes oral speech on paper. We know that speaking is a movement. And the text is not an unprepared speech, but a

constant process of pre-recorded on paper, following the rules of language units. He also showed the dual nature of the text - static and moving sides. If we break it down, if it is described in turn in different units, then there are signs of immobility (implicit). If the text is produced (read), the message is re-encoded. In this case, if the above is the first, the second is the semantic code, the combination of nouns that occur to understand the text, and the third is the culture code. Provides the necessary information from the culture of that time, the fourth - the hermeneutic code, a formulated set of tasks and answers in the message, the fifth - a symbolic code, the internal psychological causes of closed summary messages. Modern education is based on a new paradigm of education - from "viable" knowledge to the idea of "lifelong" education, based on scientific-cognitive, exploratory, creative activities in the formation of the individual. Therefore, education is a priority, influencing the psychology of the individual. And the connection of psychology with linguistics is psycholinguistics, in the aspect of which the theory of knowledge is considered. Cognition is formed by listening, recognizing, understanding, and seeing. Such comprehensive competence can be instilled in an individual through the method of text analysis in linguistics. Today's topical issue is a special consideration of methodological approaches to teaching all disciplines in connection with changes in the content, form, and structure of education.

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